

Recognizing the Work Values and Motivational Drives as Circumstances of Management Skills of Master Teachers

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ABSTRACT

Published Online: December 20, 2024

The demanding work of master teachers in the modern education system is tough and exhausting both mentally and physically. The researchers realized that these challenges can be a part of the master teacher's work commitment. This study aimed to determine the significant influence of work values and motivational drives of master teachers on their management skills. This study utilized the descriptive correlational method participated by 105 master teachers who were identified through the purposive sampling method in Davao del Norte and Tagum City divisions. The findings of the study indicated that the provision relating to the level of work values, motivational drives, and management skills of master teachers in Davao del Norte and Tagum City divisions were evident or always observed. Moreover, work values and motivation were both significant circumstances in management skills. Master teachers should be supported and empowered, particularly those who continuously cultivate their beliefs, attitudes, values, and commitments, as these qualities are vital in driving professional growth and fostering a positive educational environment.

KEYWORDS:

work values, motivational drives, management skills, descriptive correlational research design, master teachers, Davao del Norte, Tagum City

I. INTRODUCTION

Work Values are beliefs about what is worth and essential at work. They give a sense of meaning and purpose and influence how individuals lead their work lives. When a career aligns with one's values, one tends to feel motivated and engaged at work, gain job satisfaction, and share more in common with co-workers. Likewise, motivational drives can be described as increased arousal and a person's internal motivation to achieve a specific goal or purpose. For instance, when an individual is thirsty, they will feel motivated to reduce the drive by drinking water. These two variables are very vital in the Management Skills of Master Teachers.

Master teachers must possess expertise in student learning, practice and pedagogy, content area, and commitment to their work. To be a leader in the educational institution, Master Teachers are viewed as highly proficient individuals in their respective schools or divisions.

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**Cite this Article: Mardyn P. Marimon, Jeniemer B. Aranguez, Marleonie Bauyot (2024). Recognizing the Work Values and Motivational Drives as Circumstances of Management Skills of Master Teachers. International Journal of Social Science and Education Research Studies, 4(12), 1329-1334*

They work hand in hand with the school heads in the supervision of teachers. Moreover, personal values drive their goals and behaviors at school and can support subjective well-being and an individual sense of self-efficacy. The master teachers are independent learners who strive to improve their learning to deliver effective education to the students and their peers.

Motivation is among the most extensively studied subjects in organizational psychology worldwide (Madjid & Samsudin, 2021). Individuals may be driven by several elements of the work-life milieu. Understanding how to inspire your staff can guarantee they exert their utmost effort daily and assist the organization in achieving its objectives.

This study aims to explore and investigate the relationship between work values and motivational drives as circumstances in the management skills of master teachers. This study further underscores the need of acknowledging work values and motivational factors in enhancing the management competencies of master teachers, hence fostering enhanced educational leadership and teaching results.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to explore and investigate the relationship between work values and motivational drives as circumstances in the management skills of master teachers in Davao City and Tagum City Divisions. The study sought explicitly to answer the following questions:

1. Determine the status of the work values, motivational drives, and management skills of Master Teachers in the Davao Region division.
2. Determine the significance of the singular and combined influence of work values and motivational drives on management skills.

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1. The schematic diagram shows the dependent variable, the management skills of master teachers as significantly influenced by the independent variables, the level of their work values and motivational drives.

Figure. 1. The Schematic diagram showing the relationship of the independent variables and the dependent variable.

IV. METHODS

This study employed a quantitative research design using the descriptive-correlation method. There were 105 master teachers from Davao del Norte and Tagum City divisions. These master teachers were purposively chosen and must have served as master teachers for at least five years. The survey questionnaire about work values was adapted from Mc Clean (2009), the motivational drives were adapted from de Oliveira et al. (2022), and the management skills were adapted from the study of Kamete (2014). The research instrument utilized a five-point Likert Rating Scale Type of questionnaire. It was divided into three parts. Part 1 showed the independent variables that contained statements about work values and motivational drives of master teachers. In contrast, part 2 showed the dependent variable that contained statements on the management skills of master teachers with the socio-demographic profile of the respondent. Research

instrument was validated by three panel of experts to ensure its validity and reliability. The reliability coefficients of the three research instruments used were 0.79 for work values of master teachers, 0.81 for motivational drives, and 0.79 for management skills, indicating acceptable reliability for all instruments. The acceptable reliability coefficients imply that the research instruments used were consistent and dependable in measuring the work values, motivational drives, and management skills of master teachers, ensuring credible data for analysis. Data collection involved seeking a letter permission signed by Course Professor of the Graduate School, asking approval from the school division Superintendents and school heads of Davao del Norte and Tagum City divisions, and administering the survey questionnaires to the respondents. After administering the survey, the results were tallied, analyzed, and interpreted statistically. Furthermore, in analyzing the data, the following statistical tools were used namely frequency count, average weighted mean, standard deviation (SD), and Pearson r, and multiple regression analysis. Likewise, ethical concerns were observed in the design of this research work.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Status of the Work Values, Motivational Drives, and Management Skills of Master Teachers in the Davao Region Division

1.1. Status of Work Values of Master Teachers

Presented in table 1.1 is the status of work values of master teachers that has two indicators: achievement and responsibility. Responsibility obtained the higher between the two indicators which has a mean of 4.73 with a very high description. All statements under this variable have the exact description of Very High. The findings reveal that achievement and responsibility are important traits of master teachers, with achievement denoting their sustained competence in teaching and responsibility highlighting their commitment to students, families, and the wider educational community. The results underscore the significance of these work values, indicated by an overall weighted mean of 4.67, categorized as "very high," implying that these characteristics are deeply ingrained among the respondents.

Additionally, a standard deviation of 0.621 implies minimal variability in responses, reflecting a high level of agreement among participants. The analysis highlights the items with the greatest and lowest mean ratings within the category to offer a comprehensive view of the data.

This finding parallels the idea that leaders' roles, as Pont (2020) explained, may include organizational, pedagogical, and educational responsibilities. Depending on the circumstances, school leaders are called upon to organize schedules, implement curriculum, conduct extracurricular activities, conduct testing, and conduct teacher evaluations.

1.2. Status of Motivational Drives of Master Teachers

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Shown in table 1.2 is the status of motivational drives of master teachers which has two indicators: internal and external. Between the two indicators, internal motivation obtained the higher mean of 4.49, with a very high description. This indicator consists of five statements. Of these, the item "I find very much enjoy my daily work." my work" gained the highest mean of 4.73, and the item "I like performing most of my work processes" was the lowest, with a mean of 4.35.

Table 1.1. Status of Work Values of Master Teacher

Work Values	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Achievement			
1. I believe that my work alleviates my morale.	4.55	.541	Very High
2. I understand that working hard will promote my whole being.	4.54	.568	Very High
3. I work hard to achieve my desired goal in teaching.	4.73	.494	Very High
4. I work hard to remove my worries in life.	4.4	.573	Very High
5. I felt that working with the team would give me a degree of fulfillment.	4.45	.592	Very High
Sub-Mean	4.54	.568	Very High
Responsibility			
1. I always consider being high in self-monitoring	4.37	.593	Very High
2. I show a genuine concern for their students' academic welfare (teacher mentees).	4.40	.560	Very High
3. I possess a deep sense of humanity and a seemingly boundless capacity for caring about others.	4.70	.494	Very High
4. I establish high academic standards.	4.73	.494	Very High
5. I show a genuine concern for their students' academic welfare	4.39	.558	Very High
Sub-Mean	4.51	.674	Very High
Overall Mean	4.67	.621	Very High

Likewise, the external motivation indicator obtains a sub-mean of 4.31 with a description of very high. This indicator consists of five statements, and among these five, the item "I must contribute to the common good, especially to the teacher's mentees" gains the highest mean of 4.49, and

the item "I see my work as necessary for my students and co-teachers" is the lowest with a mean of 3.94.

It shows the status of a motivational drive of the master teachers. This variable obtained an overall weighted mean of 4.71 with a description of very high. The survey participants' responses established an overall standard deviation of 0.596. Thus, a holistic understanding of internal and external motivations is essential for creating conditions supporting master teachers in their roles.

These findings agree that superiors try to motivate their employees intrinsically and guide subordinates to long-term, overarching goals, for example, by conveying attractive visions and communicating the typical path to goal achievement (Reid & Dold, 2020). Schunk and DiBenedetto (2020) regard motivation as a function of agency, monitoring progress toward a goal, and the individual's sense of perceived capabilities to learn and perform actions.

Moreover, the findings are similar to TDK (2020) in that this motivation concept comes from the word "more," which means mobilization, and it is defined as the essential power source that determines the direction, violence, and determination of behavior.

Likewise, motivation is internal and external motives, desires, and wishes that direct, empower, and control people's actions by affecting them (Güzel et al., 2020). Teachers working at schools may exhibit low motivation due to reasons such as physical conditions, job satisfaction, type of control exerted, and wage, and they may exhibit high motivation due to reasons such as job satisfaction, positive interpersonal relations, and pleasure taken from the work (Ada et al., 2018).

Table 1.2. Status of Motivational Drives of Master Teachers

The Motivational Drive	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Internal Motivation			
1. I very much enjoy my daily work.	4.73	.494	Very High
2. I greatly enjoy teaching for my teachers' mentees and classroom students.	4.44	.553	Very High
3. I like performing most of my work processes	4.35	.586	Very High
4. I feel good working as a teacher mentor.	4.40	.560	Very High
5. I consider the task of teaching personally meaningful.	4.54	.568	Very High
Sub-Mean	4.49	.552	Very High
External Motivation			
1. I believe in risking personal loss to help society.	4.45	.592	Very High

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2. I am willing to risk a personal loss to help society.	4.54	.568	Very High
3. I like performing most of my work processes.	4.17	.677	High
4. I must contribute to the common good, especially to the teacher's mentees.	4.49	.543	Very High
5. I see my work as necessary for my students and co-teachers.	3.94	.827	High
Sub-Mean	4.31	.641	Very High
Overall Mean	4.71	.596	Very High

1.3. Status of Management Skills of Master Teachers

Presented in table 1.3 is the status of management skills of master teachers which has two indicators: conceptual skills and leadership skills. Among the two indicators, conceptual skills obtained the highest sub-mean of 4.43, with a very high description. All statements under this variable have the same description of very high. Moreover, Conceptual Skills indicators, with the statement “I require communication and attention to relationships with others,” observed the highest mean rating of 4.73, and “I measure a manager's intelligence” with the lowest mean rating of 4.18.

Leadership Skills gained the second-highest sub-mean rating of 4.35, with very high descriptions. All statements under this variable have the same description of very high. Moreover, the statement “I use my emotional energy to motivate others” got the highest mean rating of 4.73. In contrast, the statement “I am practical with the detailed aspects of my life” got the lowest mean rating of 4.04. On the other hand, the indicator with the lowest sub-mean is Leadership Skills. This indicator gains a sub-mean rating of 4.38 with a description of very high.

As a summary, it shows the status of the master teachers' management skills. This variable obtained an overall weighted mean of 4.35 with a description rating of very high. The standard deviation of 0.540 established from the survey participants' responses indicates a small range of dispersion, which denotes homogeneity in their perceptions. The results presentation focused on the highest mean rating and lowest mean of the category.

This finding is similar with the idea of Gul (2021) that emphasized, time management is an essential element of school organization where teachers are expected to perform different responsibilities apart from the teaching-learning process at the institutions.

Table 1.3. Status of Management Skills of Master Teachers

Management Skills	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Conceptual Skills			
1. I allow a manager to visualize the entire organization and work with ideas and the relationships between abstract concepts.	4.55	.541	Very High
2. I require communication and attention to relationships with others	4.73	.494	Very High
3. I need to get the work done; they are the techniques, practices, tools, and processes needed by front-line employees in the manager's functional area.	4.48	.543	Very High
4. I measure a manager's intelligence.	4.18	.628	High
5. I stay the same no matter where in the pyramid a manager is, but top managers are more skilled in each area.	4.24	.655	Very High
Sub-Mean	4.43	.441	Very High
Leadership Skills			
1. I am practical with the detailed aspects of my life.	4.04	.701	High
2. I usually know how people will respond to a new idea or personal.	4.40	.560	Very High
3. I enjoy responding to people's requests and concerns.	4.48	.606	Very High
4. I use my emotional energy to motivate others.	4.73	.494	Very High

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5. I can sense the emotional undercurrents in my group.	4.28	.660	Very High
Sub-Mean	4.38	.604	Very High
Overall Mean	4.35	.540	Very High

This finding is parallel with Montenegro's (2022) statement, which underscored a positive relationship between teachers' time management techniques and their class performance. The study also inferred that teachers' lesson planning techniques were very effective for their class performance due to effective time management.

Moreover, this finding is similar to the study (Arop Festus et al., 2019), which showed that teachers' performance is interlinked with head teachers' managerial skills, and effective managerial skills will be the performance of the teaching staff. It depends upon the head teacher's conceptual skills and how much he/she is creative, innovative, and object-oriented.

Circumstances of Work Values and Motivational Drives on Management Skills

Table 2 shows the regression analysis to determine the influence of work values and motivational drives on the management skills of master teachers. As shown, both of these predictors significantly circumstance the management skills of master teachers, as supported by the magnitude of their respective p-values, which are all less than 0.05. Between the two determinants, work values ($b=.141$, $p<.05$) and motivational drives ($b=.687$, $p\text{-value}<.05$), motivational drives are the better predictor since for every unit increase of this variable, a corresponding increase of .697 is realized in the management skills of master teacher, as compared to an increase of .130 contributed by a unit increase of Work Values.

Meanwhile, the R^2 value of $=.611524$ suggests that the work values and motivational drive predictors can explain 61.2% of the variance in the management skills of master teachers. This provides empirical evidence that the two independent variables can account for and explain the variability of master teachers' management skills.

In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, with regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (99.700) and F-statistic were significant $p<.005$, indicating that the model is a better predictor.

This finding aligned with the study conducted by Cena et al. (2021), which explored the work values of Filipino teachers and examined their influence on organizational commitment. Further, this finding is reinforced by the study of Manalo et al. (2020), which emphasized the critical role of motivated and committed employees in enhancing

organizational performance. Their research revealed a significant positive correlation between employee motivation and organizational commitment.

Table 2. Circumstances of Work Values and Motivational Drives on Management Skills

Predictors (Management Skills)	Beta Coefficients	t	p-value	Interpretation
Work Values	.141	2.07	0.03	Significant
Motivational Drives	.687	11.0	0.00	Significant

$R=.782$, $R\text{-square}=.611524$, $F=99.700$, $P<.05$

VI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Considering the status of work values, motivational drives, and management skills of master teachers in Davao del Norte and Tagum City divisions were often observed.

Moreover, work values and motivation are both significant circumstances in management skills. However, motivational drives were a better determinant than work values.

On the other hand, the insight shared by master teachers regarding the role of work values and motivational drives in their management skills resulted in the fact that they were crucial to their management efforts. The master teachers were very grateful for these meaningful experiences that made them more reliable in the future. The work values and motivational drives of master teachers significantly shape their effectiveness and impact within schools. It was truly a nice feeling for them to share these meaningful experiences.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, the following are considered as recommendations:

In terms of the work values of the master teachers, all indicators were rated very high. This can still be consistently very high if the education department could devise creative ways aside from the usual salary and remuneration they offer.

The variable motivational drives of master teachers were rated very high. However, among the indicators, willingness to risk a personal loss to help society was rated very high. This rating can still be sustained at a very high level if master teachers are afforded opportunities to advance in their educational qualifications and professional competence through scholarships and grants that are friendly and attractive in terms of requirements.

Regarding the management skills of the master teachers, among the two indicators, conceptual skills and leadership skills, all got a very high rating. However, the lowest indicator that obtained the lowest rating is leadership

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skills. The rating can still be sustained at a very high level since the low result suggests the need for master teachers to improve their leadership skills.

The significance of work values and motivational drives on management skills was that both of these predictors significantly circumstance the management skills of master teachers. Addressing these challenges effectively can lead to enhanced work goals and improved student performance, but it necessitates a supportive school environment that values and invests in master teachers. Experiences challenge the master teachers, and these challenges can lead to more effective teaching and improved student educational outcomes. Given these, the intensive implementation of the continuing career professional growth formulated by the Department of Education (DepEd) is recommended.

Master teachers should be supported and empowered, particularly those who continuously cultivate their beliefs, attitudes, values, and commitments, as these qualities are vital in driving professional growth and fostering a positive educational environment.

VII. DISCLOSURE

This study was undertaken exclusively for academic purposes as a requirement for our quantitative research subject. All collected data were handled with the highest level of confidentiality, ensuring the anonymity of participants. This research was devoid of any potential conflicts of interest or financial benefits. Participation was voluntary, and individuals may withdraw at any moment without consequences. The results of this study were utilized exclusively for academic dissemination and were not used for any commercial or unlawful uses.

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